

Assessment of Perceptions on Utilization of E-Learning Mode during Covid-19 Outbreak among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the perceptions on utilization of e-learning mode during Covid-19 outbreak among secondary school students in Osun State, Nigeria. The paper examined the perceptions on relevance and challenges on utilization of e-learning. It assessed the relationship between male and female secondary school students' perceptions on the use of e-learning mode as well as and determined the relationships between public and private secondary school students' perceptions, respectively.

The study employed a descriptive research design, and the population consisted of all public and private school students in Osogbo local government area of Osun State during the 2020/2021 Academic Session. A sample size of 125 male and 125 female students making a total number of 250 were selected using convenience sampling technique. A questionnaire tagged "Students' Perceptions on Utilization of E-Learning Mode during Covid-19 Outbreak in Osun State (SPUELMCOOS)" was used for data collection. The collected data was analysed using percentages and ANOVA. The findings of the study revealed that secondary school students generally value electronics, especially television, as a major audiovisual channel for mass education. The finding also showed that e-learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused. The study's conclusion was that secondary school students had similar perceptions on utilization of e-learning during the Covid-19 outbreak in Osun State, Nigeria. The study recommended that the Nigerian government should not relent in its effort by providing necessary support to overcome challenges faced by e-learning among secondary school students.

Keyword: Educational System, Coronavirus, Covid-19 Outbreak, E-Learning Mode, Television, Secondary School Students

Introduction

Without exaggerating, the cornerstone of any national development, whether in a developed, developing, or underdeveloped country, is education. For all human societies to flourish and endure, they must acquire the necessary abilities, information, and experience (Onocha, 2013). Nonetheless, education enhances the country's human capital. An individual needs education for all-around development and to become a valuable member of society. Learning results in the development of a person's moral character, physical prowess, spiritual integrity, cultural refinement, emotional stability, and intelligent self-sufficiency from birth throughout life. Therefore, learning has occurred if there is a permanent change in behaviour as a result of practice and experience.

There are two types of learning: distance learning and conventional learning. Conventional learning, for example, is a type of teaching-learning arrangement where learners and instructors participate in the teaching-learning activities together (Ordu, 2021). Teachers and students are physically present in the classroom during this type of instruction. As opposed to this, distance learning is defined as a type of learning that takes place when a teacher is not physically present, typically with the assistance of one or more instructional media and resources (Harry, & Khan, 2000; Odewumi & Ajala, 2017). Raman (2011) observed that technology in the classroom changes the ways learning occurs; learners are no longer restricted to the four walls of classrooms, but rather have lots of opportunities to explore the vast volumes of available information on the internet to enhance meaningful learning. Distance learning is subdivided into open learning, flexible learning, and e-learning. In other words, e-learning is made possible by electronic technology, as defined by Kyari, Adiuku-Brown, Abechi, and Adedokun (2018). This includes online learning, computer-based learning, and virtual classrooms where content is delivered through e-networks, audio or video tape, satellite TV, video conferencing, CD-ROM, iPods, e-mails, wireless, and mobile technology.

Electronic-learning offers many benefits to students: it enables them to have access to many resources and tools, not be bound by place or time, study at their own pace, skip material already learned, and use a variety of tools to fit their own style. In distance learning, learners are separated geographically and by possible time from the instructor; hence, synchronous forms of e-learning have been in use to provide multi-outlet chances to meaningfully engage the students and therefore aid comprehension and retention. Abidoye and Aderere (2019) revealed that most aspects of instructional activities globally today have been witnessing technological transformation, such as e-mail, e-conference, e-teaching, e-presentation, e-library, and online learning. These e-learning tools are easily utilised by learners to improve the successful teaching and learning of the subjects.

Generally speaking, e-learning refers to the delivery of instruction via the internet, mobile devices, satellite television, audio, video tape, and radio. According to a study by Karunarathne et al. (2020), e-learning is a flexible and effective alternative method of instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic. Prior to the advent of the internet, Ternholm (2011) and Kannadasan, Muthuchamy, and Amalorpavam (2019) contended that television was the most widely used media. Television is still regarded as one of the most popular e-tools for distance learning in the modern era. One of the most effective ways to deliver education is through television, which offers distant learners both audio and visual effects to illustrate concepts and procedures. According to earlier research, television is widely used to provide distance learning to students worldwide (Olakulehin & Salawu, 2006; Akhter, 2011; Kunucen, Kaya, Mirici, Kunucen & Ozturk, 2003). Thus, if they so choose, all students can benefit from home-study television. The study by Olakulehin and Salawu (2006) went on to explain the educational value of television in the following ways: it can reach a large number of geographically dispersed students with a single instructional message; it can boost students' motivation and interest even when they are geographically apart from their teachers; and it can provide essential teaching resources because all students should be able to watch the broadcast.

Both humans and animals can contract coronavirus diseases, such as the respiratory illness coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), which can spread from one person to another (Yadav, & Mohite, 2020). According to Yao, Ye, and Zhang (2020), an infection can cause symptoms to last for two to fourteen days. These symptoms include fever, dyspnea, and coughing. Spreading the virus can occur through respiratory droplets from an infected person's cough or sneeze, touching an infected person's hands or face, touching doorknobs that other infected people have touched, or touching a surface or object contaminated with the virus and then touching their own mouth, nose, or possibly their eyes (Yadav & Mohite, 2020; Keyaerts, Vijgen & Maes, 2004).

The Zambian Ministry of Health announced at a press conference in mid-March 2020 that all schools, colleges, and universities would be permanently closed on Friday, March 20, 2020, due to concerns about the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, which had reportedly destroyed most of China, the United States, Italy, Spain, and other regions of Europe and Africa. Because many public and private schools administer assessment tests at the end of each of the three terms of the academic year, this meant that secondary school students in the majority of public and private schools ended the second term of the academic year 2020 without writing their end-of-term examinations. It appears that there were few literatures on COVID-19 in Nigerian educational studies. The existing literature (Wu & McGoogan, 2020; Kraemer et al., 2020; Hopman, Allegranzi, & Mehtar, 2020; Chinazzi et al., 2020) is closely linked to medical research. This is not because the COVID-19 pandemic has not had an impact on education directly; rather, it is because research on education has not often taken into account how diseases may affect how well students are taught around the world. Every aspect of human life has been directly impacted by COVID-19 as a result of its rapid spread. Employees in the medical field are working extremely hard to find a medical cure for this pandemic. Because businesses are closing on a daily basis and human movement is restricted both within and across borders, economists are working on ways to manage the economic impact of this epidemic on the nation's economy (Kraemer et al., 2020). Unexpectedly, a disease that first surfaced in the Wuhan region of China spread quickly throughout the country and other countries (Wickramasinghe et al., 2020).

On the other hand, even in situations where childhood infection rates are low, school closures are a crucial part of social distancing strategies to slow the illness's spread and stop cases from rising too quickly, which would put strain on health services. The exact timing of the closures, the population's age distribution, and the length of the closure will all have an impact on how successful they are in containing the spread of infection. The US Centres for Disease Control (US-CDC) have released new guidelines that the school closures are required to facilitate contact tracing and decontamination, particularly in cases where COVID-19 cases are found in schools. It also highlights how important it is for promoting social distancing.

According to a study by Karunarathne et al. (2020), many students have trouble using e-learning due to technical problems, poor internet connectivity, expensive chargers, lack of IT literacy, and health problems like eye problems that prevent them from using e-learning. According to the study by Aboyade, Madu, and Ajayi (2023), a number of factors, such as

inadequate funding, inadequate facilities, lack of orientation, poor internet connectivity, inconsistent poor supply, and a high cost of internet subscription, prevent Federal Polytechnic Ede students from adopting and using e-learning platforms.

According to Aboderin's (2015) research, the primary issues were lack of computers, a lack of internet connection, lack of e-learning tools and resources for students, expensive software, and erratic power sources. It should be mentioned that e-learning presents a number of difficulties. In order to enhance the e-learning initiative in Nigeria, basic amenities like computers, electricity, and the Internet are still lacking, as demonstrated by a later study by Kyari et al. (2018). This implies that the problem of inadequate infrastructure will continue.

Madhubhashini (2021) noted that Covid-19 outbreak has made a serious impact on socio-economic, cultural, political, education sectors locally and globally. He further stated that Covid-19 has a negative impact on the whole education system from primary education to higher education. According to the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) report in 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic has also made a serious negative impact on socio-economic, cultural, political and education sectors in Sri Lanka. In this context, the government and private schools, universities and the other education institutions are also facing some challenges with the traditional mode of education. Therefore, government and private institutions introduced some alternative teaching and learning mechanisms via new technology. It is important to note that school closure can have an impact on the labour market by placing more of a burden on parents, who must either stay at home with their children or find alternative arrangements, which is particularly bad if examinations like the WAEC, GCE, and NECO are closed. Given the circumstances in Osun State, e-learning via television is seems to be more effective mode of instruction in the state secondary schools and it is hoped that this will create an environment that will offers learners an exciting opportunity to improve their learning experiences.

It has been observed that the outbreak of COVID-19 has caused unprecedented disruptions in the education sector worldwide, and Osun State in Nigeria is no exception. In response to the closure of schools and the enforcement of social distancing measures, educational institutions have resorted to e-learning as a mean of ensuring continuity in learning. While this shift to online platforms has been necessary to curb the expansion of the virus, it has also brought to light a number of challenges and opportunities that warrant further investigation. However, the sudden transition to e-learning has raised concerns about the quality and effectiveness of online instruction. The benefits of e-learning in the delivery of academic subjects in schools have been noted by the researchers (Olakulehin & Salawu, 2006; Kannan, Muthuchamy, & Amalorpavam, 2019). According to these authors, television is widely used to facilitate distance learning for students around the globe. It is unclear how likely the teaching-learning process has improved among secondary school students with the use of e-learning during Covid-19 out-break in Osun State. Thus, this study evaluated secondary school students' perceptions on utilization of e-learning method during Covid-19 outbreak in Osun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to assess secondary school students' perceptions on utilization of e-learning mode during Covid-19 out-break in Osun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State
2. Assess challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State
3. Examine if there is a significant relationship between male and female students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State; and
4. Examine if there is a significant relationship between public and private school students on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Research Questions

Two research questions were asked and answered. These are:

1. What are the perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?
2. What are the challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?

Hypothesis

1. H₀₁. There is no significant relationship between male and female students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

2. H_{02} . There is no significant relationship between private and public students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Methodology

Research Design

This research used a descriptive survey research design, consulting a group of people to gather data from a small number of them deemed representative of the entire group. This approach was deemed appropriate for this study because it uses selected samples drawn from a large population to determine events as they actually occur without the intervention of outside researchers.

Population, Sample size and sampling technique

The population of the study consisted of all public and private secondary school students in Osogbo local government area of Osun State during the 2020/2021 Academic Session. A sample size of 125 male and 125 female students making a total number of 250 respondents were selected from the targeted population using convenience sampling technique. One hundred and twenty-five students were equally selected from both public and private secondary schools, respectively.

Research Instrument

The instrument employed in this work is a self-designed questionnaire tagged “Students’ Perceptions on Utilization of E-Learning Mode during Covid-19 Outbreak in Osun State (SPUELMCOOS)” with 4 Likert response mode of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) which was used for data collection.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The questionnaire was subjected to content and face validity and for the reliability of the instrument, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to test the internal consistency of the questionnaire. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient showed a high level of internal consistency with a value of 0.82. Thus, it showed that the questionnaire used in this study is reliable.

Procedure for Data Collection

In order to collect data for this study, the researchers made use of lockdown ease period (Mondays-Thursdays) in Osun State to embarked on door-to-door administration of the instrument on the senior secondary students in Osogbo local government area. The researchers’ personal involvement at this stage allowed them to get familiar with the respondents. They ensured that the social distancing and other medical advice were strictly observed. The researchers also ensured that the respondents were not coarse, their consent was sought and they responded willingly, thus providing opportunities for clarifications.

Data Analysis

The data collected was analysed with the use of frequency counts, simple percentages and ANOVA.

Results

Research Question One:

What are the perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?

Table 1: Analysis of Responses on Perceptions of Relevance of E-Learning during COVID-19 out-break among Secondary School Students in Osun State

Description of items	SA	A (%)	D (%)	SD(%)	Total
E-Learning has been accepted all over the world as a mean of providing distance learning to distance learners.	129(51.6%)	111(44.4%)	10(4%)	-	250(100%)
It carries essential teaching and learning materials which can be accessed by all learners.	163(65.2%)	63(25.2%)	7(2.8%)	17(6.8%)	250(100%)
	97(38.8%)	103(41.2%)	37(14.8%)	13(5.2%)	250(100%)

It is a flexible mean of transmitting most of the school subjects contents to the learners.	87(34.8%)	133(53.2%)	13(5.2%)	17(6.8%)	250(100%)
Electronics learning can arouse the interest of the learners.	99(39.6%)	123(49.2%)	21(8.4%)	7(2.8%)	250(100%)
Learning through electronics makes it to be real and permanent.	143(57.2%)	91(36.4%)	16(6.4%)	-	250(100%)
E-learning via television is the best tool to deliver instructional contents in a situation where learners and instructors are separated by geographical locations.					

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

Table 1 above presents the findings of the study on the views of students on the relevance of electronics learning in senior secondary schools in Osun State. The finding showed that 129 (51.6%) and 111 (44.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning has been accepted all over the world as a means of providing distance learning to distance learners, respectively, while 10 (4%) of the respondents disagreed. The finding also revealed that 163 (65.2%) and 63 (25.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning carries essential teaching and learning materials that can be accessed by all learners, while 7 (2.8%) and 17 (6.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. Either electronics learning is a flexible mean of transmitting most of the school subjects' contents to the learners or not, 97 (38.8%) and 103 (41.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning is a flexible mean of transmitting most of the school subjects' contents to the learners, while 37 (14.8%) and 13 (5.2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study indicated that 87 (34.8%) and 133 (53.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning can arouse the interest of the learners, while 13 (5.2%) and 17 (6.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

The study also reveals that 99 (39.6%) and 123 (49.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that learning through electronics makes it real and permanent, while 21 (8.4%) and 7 (2.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly agreed. The finding finally showed that 143 (57.2%) and 91 (36.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that e-learning via television is the best tool to deliver instructional contents in a situation where learners and instructors are separated by geographical locations, while 16 (6.4%) of the respondents disagreed.

Research Question Two:

What are the challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?

Table 2: Analysis of Responses on Challenges of E-Learning Utilization during COVID-19 out-break among Secondary School Students in Osun State

Description of items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD(%)	Total
It hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused.	117(46.8%)	93(37.2%)	29(11.6%)	11(4.4%)	250(100%)
Poor electricity connectivity is a challenge in using electronics learning as a mode of learning.	133(53.2%)	103(41.2%)	9(3.6%)	5(2%)	250(100%)
Electronics learning can create problem for learners with low technical skills.	129(51.6%)	113(45.2%)	7(2.8%)	1(0.4%)	250(100%)
It is not effective in any environment that has poor electricity supply.	149(59.6%)	83(33.2%)	11(4.4%)	7(2.8%)	250(100%)
	113(45.2%)	64(25.6%)	52(20.8%)	21(8.4%)	250(100%)

Improper maintenance can be a shortcoming to the usage of electronics as mode of learning.	147(58.8%)	91(36.4%)	12(4.8%)	-	250(100%)
Individual differences may not be catered for through television learning.	113(45.2%)	103(41.2%)	21(8.4%)	13(5.2%)	250(100%)
E-Learning presentation may be interrupted by technical faults and power failure.	123(49.2%)	111(44.4%)	9(3.6%)	7(2.8%)	250(100%)
Poor recording of the instructional programmes leads to loss of interest on the part of the learners.					

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

The findings of the study as presented in Table 2 revealed that 117 (46.8%) and 93 (37.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused, while 29 (11.6%) and 11 (4.4%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The finding also showed that 133 (53.2%) and 103 (41.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that poor electricity connectivity is a challenge in using electronics learning as a mode of learning, while 9 (3.6%) and 5 (2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study indicated that 129 (51.6%) and 113 (45.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning can create problems for learners with low technical skills, while 9 (3.6%) and 5 (2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. The findings of the study showed that 149 (59.6%) and 83 (33.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, that electronics learning is not effective in any environment that has poor electricity supply, while 11 (4.4%) and 7 (2.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study also revealed that 113 (45.2%) and 64 (25.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that improper maintenance can be a shortcoming to the usage of electronics as a mode of learning, while 52 (20.8%) and 21 (8.4%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. Moreover, 147 (58.8%) and 91 (36.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that individual differences may not be catered for through television learning, while 12 (4.8%) of the respondents disagreed. The finding also showed that 113 (45.2%) and 103 (41.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning presentations may be interrupted by technical faults and power failure, while 21 (8.4%) and 13 (5.2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study finally revealed that 123 (49.2%) and 111 (44.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that poor recording of the instructional programmes leads to loss of interest on the part of the learners, while 9 (3.6%) and 7 (2.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

H₀₁:

There is no significant relationship between male and female students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Table 3: The One-Way Anova Analysis on Relationship between Male and Female Students' Perception on Utilization of E-Learning during COVID-19 out-break among Secondary Schools in Osun State.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	60.516	1	60.516	441.827	.000
Within Groups	33.968	248	.137		
Total	94.484	249			

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

Table 3 above showed that F is 441.827 p<0.000. This implies that there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State, was accepted.

H₀₂:

There is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Table VI: The One-Way Anova Analysis on Relationship between Public and Private Students' Perception on Utilization of E-Learning COVID-19 out-break among Secondary Schools in Osun State.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	46.766	2	23.383	367.069	.000
Within Groups	15.734	247	.064		
Total	62.500	249			

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

Table 3 above showed that F is (367.069). This implies that there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between private and public students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools, was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The study was carried out to assess secondary school students' perceptions on utilization of e-learning mode during Covid-19 out-break in Osun State, Nigeria. Two hundred and fifty (250) participants were involved in the study. The first research objective was to assess perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State. The findings of the study showed that electronics learning has been accepted all over the world as a mean of providing distance learning to distance learners especially during the pandemic period. The possible reason for this may be as a result of the fact that from time immemorial television has been the major audio-visual channel for mass education. This finding is in support of Abidoye and Fakokunde (2015) who explained that e-learning is relevant in the teaching and learning of social studies in secondary schools. The finding also revealed that electronics learning carries essential teaching and learning materials that can be accessed by all learners. This finding agreed with the study of Larson (2018) who found that majority of the users of OPAC were satisfied with the benefits derived from using Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC). The finding of the study indicates that electronics learning can arouse the interest of the learners. This finding corroborates with the findings of Odewumi and Ajala (2017) who claimed that learning through mobile digital devices could be interesting and create easy communication between students and teachers. The finding equally showed that e-learning via television is the best tool to deliver instructional contents in a situation where learners and instructors are separated by geographical locations.

The second research objective was to assess challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State. The results of the findings revealed that electronic learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused. The finding also showed that poor electricity connectivity is a challenge in using electronics learning as a mode of learning. The finding is in consonance with the study of Aboderin (2015), and Aboyade, Madu, and Ajayi (2023). The findings of the study indicated that electronic learning can create problems for learners with low technical skills. The findings of the study showed that electronics learning is not effective in any environment that has a poor electricity supply. The findings of the study also revealed that improper maintenance can be a shortcoming in the use of electronics as a mode of learning. The finding also showed that electronics learning presentations may be interrupted by technical faults and power failures. This finding also agreed with the findings of Afolabi and Abidoye (2016) whose study identified poor power supply, inadequate ICT knowledge, poor internet connections and poor funding as hindrances to using e - learning tools in learning environment in Nigerian Universities.

The third research objective was also to examine if there is a significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State. Data collected on research hypothesis I, which states that there is no significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools. The result of the study revealed

that there is a significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

The fourth research question was to examine if there is a significant relationship between public and private school students on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State. Data collected on research hypothesis II, which states that there is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools. The finding showed that there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of E-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools, was accepted.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, secondary school students value electronics in general, with television being one of the main audiovisual channels for mass education. The finding also showed that e-learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused. The results of the study equally indicated that there is a significant relationship between male and female secondary school students' perceptions on the use of e-learning mode. The study's conclusion was that secondary school students had similar perceptions on utilization of e-learning during the Covid-19 outbreak in Osun State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion of the study:

1. To guarantee the smooth integration of electronics in education, students should be given access to sufficient resources and training to address the obstacles they may encounter.
2. The study encourages inclusivity and engagement and puts into practice strategies that take into account the divergent perspectives of male and female students regarding e-learning.
3. The study recommended that the Nigerian government should not relent in its effort by providing necessary support to overcome challenges faced by e-learning among secondary school students.
4. Students' experiences with online and electronic learning should be evaluated on a regular basis, and adjustments made as needed based on their feedback.
5. To create an environment that is favourable for learning for students, teachers should be provided with the necessary assistance and training they need to successfully integrate electronics into their lesson plans.

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